

STRUCTURAL GRAPHENE COMPOSITES: TAKING THE LESSONS OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES THROUGH TO BULK COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The exceptional properties of graphene make it a promising reinforcement in structural polymer composite materials [1]. We have previously studied the micromechanics of graphene composites using Raman spectroscopy to map the strain in model composite systems comprising of single graphene flakes [2,3,4]. We have showed that the graphene behaviour can be modelled using conventional composite theory despite being an atomic layer. For example, graphene follows the shear lag theory for short fibres, with a critical minimum flake length of 3 microns being required for good reinforcement. We have also shown that the modulus of graphene flakes reduces with the thickness of the flake due to poor internal stress transfer between the graphene layers [5]. We have now transferred these design rules for graphene composites to bulk systems produced by solvent casting (PVOH-graphene composites, [6]), twin screw compounding (PMMA-graphene and PP-graphene composites [7,8]) and hot curing (e.g. epoxy-graphene composites). We have explored the role of polymer-graphene interface on the properties of these composites through using different surface functionalities on the graphene flakes. The role of flake length has also been studied by using few layer graphene with controlled lengths from 100 nm to 20 micron. The 20 micron few layer flakes show particular promise as they are long enough to give good reinforcement, yet do not aggregate even at high loadings (> 10 vol%).

1. INTRODUCTION

Graphene is an atomically-thin, two-dimensional honeycomb material with extraordinary electronic, thermal and mechanical properties, [9–10] which makes it an ideal candidate for a wide variety of applications including sensors, batteries, supercapacitors and hydrogen storage [11]. A promising application is the incorporation of graphene into polymer matrices in order to improve the electrical, thermal and/or mechanical properties [1,13,14]. The micromechanics of such composites has been studied by using Raman spectroscopy to probe the strain behaviour of individual flakes embedded in polymer beams [2-5]. This technique uses the shift of the Raman band positions with displacement to map the strain in the sample at a micron spatial resolution. It also takes advantage of graphene being Raman resonant such that a Raman spectrum can be collected from a monolayer of atoms in less than one minute. Typically the position of the 2D Raman band is studied as it is a two-phonon scattering event and thus gives the highest shift rate with strain (60 cm⁻¹ per %). It has been shown in such systems that micromechanically exfoliated monolayer graphene can achieve its theoretically predicted effective modulus of 1 TPa [2]. A similar value is also found for bilayer graphene flakes within polymer composites. However, the modulus is found to drop as the number of layers within a flake is increased due to the easy internal shear between the graphene layers. This internal shearing leads to the modulus of a 5-layer flake dropping to 0.6 TPa flake [5]. This decrease in modulus with thickness would initially suggest that one should use monolayer or bilayer graphene to reinforce a composite as they have the highest modulus. However, taking the rule of mixtures as the simplest model for the modulus a composite, one can see that the degree of reinforcement is a function of both the loading fraction and modulus. The maximum achievable loading fraction is strongly influenced by the graphene being thinner than the polymer molecules surrounding it. For example,

monolayer graphene has a theoretical maximum volume fraction of $\sim 1/7$ assuming a perfect dispersion with the graphene perfectly aligned and coated evenly on both sides with a polymer layer that is one radius of gyration thick. Whereas, the packing density of trilayer in such a system is $1/3$. Thus taking into account the balance between the increase in volume fraction and drop in modulus with flake thickness, few layer graphene (FLG) is found to be the optimal thickness. This result is fortuitous as the majority of scalable graphene production routes produce few layer graphene (FLG).

Traditional shear lag theory predicts that the strain within a given graphene flake should build up gradually from the ends of the flake through shear forces until it is the same as that within the matrix. This shear-lag has been recently been proved experimentally through micromapping of the Raman spectra within individual flakes. This observation of the “*short fibre effect*” confirms that conventional composite theory can still be applied even to atomically thin materials. Gong *et al.* [2] found that the critical flake diameter for reinforcement was ~ 3 microns for unfunctionalised graphene, due to the relatively weak interfacial strength of 1 MPa compared to the 30 MPa found for carbon fibre–epoxy composites. (Graphene has none of the chemical or mechanical interactions of a sized carbon fibre.) Thus in summary, micromechanics predict that ideally a nanocomposite should use FLG typically 4–5 layers thick with a length of >3 microns, and more preferably >30 microns.

Herein, we investigate the effect of flake diameter on the mechanical and thermal properties of bulk thermoplastic composites at loadings relevant to structural applications. A semicrystalline (PP) and an amorphous (PMMA) matrix system were used. Gram quantities of few layer graphene (FLG) with two different diameter distributions, 5 microns and 20 microns, were prepared by reductive electrochemical exfoliation. PP/FLG composites were then prepared from 0.5 to 20 wt% loading of the two different diameter FLG samples. The mechanical properties of the composites were evaluated by tensile testing.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Few layer graphene (FLG) was produced by reductive electrochemical exfoliation of graphite. In summary, a graphite cathode was exfoliated by the intercalation of ions (TBA^+ and Li^+). The exfoliated material was collected, washed and dried, with no centrifugation or ultrasonication steps being needed. All the material produced was < 5 nm thickness with a typical thickness of 4–6 layers. The exfoliated material possessed a similar diameter as the grain size in the initial graphite, allowing the flake size to be controlled through the choice of electrode material. For this work, two average FLG flake diameters were prepared; 5 microns (5-FLG) and 20 microns (20-FLG). Further details on the exfoliation method can be found in Cooper *et al.* [15] and Abdelkader *et al.* [16].

Bulk composites were prepared by compounding the 5-FLG and 20-FLG samples at loading between 0.5 to 20 wt% into a thermoplastic using a twin screw extruder (Thermo Scientific HAAKE MiniLab micro compounder). The material was cycled for 15 minutes at 230 °C (PMMA) or at 190 °C (PP) a screw speed of 100 rpm before being extruded and manually pelletised. The extruded samples were further processed into bone shaped specimens by injection moulding (HAAKE MiniJet Piston Injection Moulding System, $T_{\text{cylinder}} = 230$ °C (PMMA) or at 190 °C (PP), $T_{\text{mould}} = 65$ °C, pressure. 740 bar kept for 10 s). Neat thermoplastic samples were processed using the same steps. Herein the PP samples prepared with the 5 and 20 micron flakes are referred to as 5-FLG/PP and 20-FLG/PP respectively. Likewise the PMMA composites are referred to as 5-FLG/PMMA and 20-FLG/PMMA respectively.

Dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC, DSC-Q100 from TA Instruments) was used to assess the crystallinity in the PP samples. Measurements were carried out under nitrogen gas from 20 to 200 °C. The samples were first heated to 200 °C to remove their thermal history, and after that they were cooled to -40 °C. Both cooling and heating were always performed at a rate of 10 °C/min. To determine the crystallization and melting properties the second heating and first cooling cycles were considered. The associated thermal parameters of crystallization (T_c) and melting (T_m) temperatures,

crystallization enthalpy (ΔH_c), heat of melting (ΔH_m), and the percentage of crystallinity (X_c) were calculated. The relative X_c was determined from the melting curves using the following expression:

$$X_c = (\Delta H_m / (1-x)\Delta H_0) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m is the crystallization enthalpy melting heat of the samples, ΔH_0 is the theoretical value of the melting heat for a 100 % crystalline PP which is 165 J/g [17], and x is the weight fraction of FLG in the sample.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DEGREE OF CRYSTALLINITY IN THE PP SYSTEM

Figure 1: The DSC curves for (a) 5-FLG/PP and (b) 20-FLG/PP composites and the crystallization temperature (c) and degree of crystallinity (d) obtained from them.

The degree of crystallinity in a semicrystalline matrix strongly affects the composite's mechanical properties. Furthermore, it is well known that nanomaterials can act as nucleation sites during cooling, increasing the degree of crystallinity compared to that of the neat polymer processed under the same conditions. Thus it was important to assess the microstructure of the polymer to ensure that any improvements seen upon the addition of the FLG could actually be attributed to the correct mechanism. Figure 1 shows the DSC traces and plots the crystallization temperature and degree of crystallization as function of FLG loading and diameter. The addition of the FLG did increase both T_c and percentage crystallinity. However, the former had a strong dependence on flake size, particularly at the higher loadings whereas the latter found to be independent of flake size. The fact that the degree of crystallinity is independent of flake size means that any difference in the mechanical

properties of the PP/5FLG and PP/20FLG samples is due to flake size effects rather than changes in the polymer’s microstructure. X-ray diffraction found that the neat polymer was pure α -phase (not shown) and the composite samples were predominantly α -phase with a little β -phase.

3.2 TENSILE PROPERTIES

The PMMA composites showed the expected glassy behavior under tensile testing and also showed significant reinforcement of the polymer by the graphene (Figure 2). For 5-FLG/PMMA composites a maximum increase of 7 % for the Young’s modulus (E) was observed for 2 wt.% loading, whereas by adding 20 wt.% of 20-FLG the modulus was increased by 74 % [18]. The addition of the graphene embrittled the polymer, with the strain to break decreasing with increasing loading (Figure 2c), as reported before with nanotubes and other graphene composites.

The tensile strengths increased with loading up to 2 wt.% for both series of composites, but then dropped at higher loadings. As with the modulus, the tensile strengths were higher for the 20-FLG/PMMA relative to the 5-FLG/PMMA composites for all the loadings studied.

Figure 2: Typical stress-strain curves of (a) 5-FLG/PMMA and (b) 20-FLG/PMMA nanocomposites at the loadings studied. (c) Variation of the stress and strain at break of the composites with loading. (d)

The Young’s modulus as function of FLG loading. The graphene oxide (GO)/PMMA data is taken from [7]. Note that these GO samples were hot pressed and then cut into dog bones, hence the small difference in modulus of the neat matrix.

The PP samples also were found to behave as glassy polymers (Figure 3) with the tensile fracture strain decreasing with increasing FLG loading. The tensile strengths of the 20-FLG remained constant with loading, whereas the tensile strength of the 5-FLG dropped for the medium loaded samples. There was no significant change within experimental error of the Young’s Modulus of the 5-FLG/PP

composites with loading. However, for the 20-FLG/PP composites a linear increase of E with loading was observed with the modulus doubling at a 20 wt.% loading.

Figure 3: Typical stress-strain curves of (a) 5-FLG/PP and (b) 20-FLG/PP nanocomposites at the loadings studied. Variation of the (c) stress and strain at break and (d) modulus of the composites with loading.

Figure 4: The modulus of different graphene composite systems, normalized to the initial modulus of the polymer matrix. The graphene oxide (GO) in PMMA data is taken from [7].

Figure 4 summarises the modulus data for both thermoplastic systems. As can be seen, the smaller diameter 5-FLG did not give rise to a significant increase in the modulus in either the PP or the PMMA. However, the larger 20-FLG did give a linear increase in modulus with loading, suggesting that the 5-FLG were beneath the critical diameter for good reinforcement. (It should be noted that

since the degree of crystallinity of the PP composites was the same regardless of the flake size, yet only the larger flakes reinforced the matrix, the role of crystallinity can be disregarded in this discussion.) The linear nature of the fits to the data in Figure 4, suggests that the system can be model to a first approximation by the rule of mixtures. Furthermore, polarised Raman spectroscopy of the samples found that the intensity of the band was independent of specimen orientation (not shown), thus it can be assumed that the graphene was randomly orientated with the samples. Thus the effective modulus of the graphene can be calculated as ~ 35 GPa, compared to a theoretical prediction of ~ 600 GPa.

It is interesting to compare the performance of the FLG in the thermoplastics with that of graphene oxide (GO), which is a highly oxidised monolayer of graphene with a C:O ratio of 3:1 and a modulus of 200-300 GPa [7]. At very low loadings, the GO has a very good effective modulus, similar to that theoretically predicted. This excellent performance is assumed to be due to its functionality enabling a good dispersion and improved interaction with the matrix. However, the modulus of the GO/PMMA composites is constant or even drops at higher loadings. This is assumed to be due to self-aggregation of the GO. Meanwhile the unfunctionalized FLG has a very low effective modulus but its performance linearly increase up to loadings of at least 20 wt% such that the maximum achievable modulus exceeds that which is possible with the GO. Overall, there appears to be a optimal degree of functionalization for good reinforcement which is between the high functionalized level of GO which has a good specific performance at low loadings but aggregates too easily and the completely unfunctionalised FLG which has a poor specific performance but can be used at very high loadings.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Nanocomposites were prepared from PP and PMMA using few layer graphene as a structural reinforcement. Two different diameter graphene samples were used, one with an average diameter of 5 microns and one with an average diameter of 20 microns. The samples prepared with the smaller flakes showed little improvement in their mechanical properties, whereas the larger flakes gave a linear improvement in modulus up to relatively high loadings of 20 wt%. This size dependence confirms on the bulk scale the previous predicted critical length for graphene based upon shear lag theory. Comparison of the graphene composites with those produced with graphene oxide suggests that future work should concentrate on establishing the balance between having sufficient functionality to have a good interface with the matrix, whilst not having so much that functionality that aggregation occurs.

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